

“Daegu Living Labs” as City Innovation Platform

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to introduce the components, operational mechanism, operational philosophy, and **sub-models** of Daegu Living Labs, and illustrate how they are bringing changes to the city by creating sustainability. Daegu Living Labs are a platform that transforms the city into superstructure and infrastructure. The superstructure is a program that trains innovation processes called '**Stimulation - Training - Facilitation - Diffusion**', aiming to increase Smart Citizens and innovation facilitators. The infrastructure is a process of co-creation with a citizen panel in a specific place, such as an alley living lab, a social living lab, and a smart living lab. The infrastructure is aimed at solving the problem in the context and involved Smart Citizens and Facilitators trained in the superstructure. The top and bottom are interconnected through Daegu Living Labs Governance and spread through the Creative City Global Forum. As Daegu Living Labs expanded its voluntary citizen panel, the city's direct democracy became more active, and the creative individual, alleys **including** living labs were linked to each other in a multi-layered manner, increasing the density of innovation in the city. Daegu Living Labs are assisting the city to substantially achieve the UN's SDGs agenda, such as Making resilient and sustainable city, ensuring learning opportunities, achieving gender equality, Building resilient infrastructure.

Keywords: *Innovation Platform, Daegu Living Labs, Resilience, Citizen Science, Social Living Lab, Alley Living Lab, Social Innovation, Sustainability Development Goals*

1 Background

Daegu is an inland city with a population of 2.4 million residents located in the south-eastern part of the Republic of Korea (100 minutes from KTX in Seoul). Daegu has played important role as the educational, industrial and cultural hub city of south-eastern Korea. Historically, the region not only displayed high receptivity for innovation but also has been the last bastion when it comes to overcoming national hardships. However, from about 25 years ago, the key industries of the city started to gradually decline, and cultural openness has been weakened.

Moreover, as global cities increasingly adopt the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals that UN issued with its goal of “Transforming our world,” Daegu was strongly calling for a dynamic City Innovation Platform led by civilians. In 2014, the Creative City Forum consisting of diverse innovators was launched: the City Innovation Platform started its operation. The former public participatory projects evolved into upgraded Living Labs by the City Innovation Platform. During the process, the platform presented various forms of Living Labs and utilized them as important tools for the city’s sustainability and resilience. In other words, the City Innovation Platform and Daegu Living Labs are evolving together through their interactions with each other.

This study aims to introduce the components, operational mechanism, operational philosophy, and sub-models of Daegu Living Labs, and to illustrate how they are making changes in the city by creating sustainability. Below are the descriptions of the evolution process of the city:

Historically, Daegu has been a leader in preserving the country in times of crisis. During the Japanese colonial period (1910-1945), it was the birthplace of the National Compensation Movement, in which the citizens voluntarily repaid the debt and tried to defend it. This movement was Korea's first donation cultural movement, which later influenced foreign repayment campaigns in China and Vietnam. Its historical significance was acknowledged globally last year, and records related to the Treasury Compensation Movement were listed as UNESCO World Heritage Sites.

Culturally, Daegu has produced countless artists representing Korea in literature, art, music, and theatre. Especially, there are concert halls where citizens can enjoy all over the city. Various music performance festivals such as classical, musical, opera, and folk, and various music education programs for citizens, enhance the creativity of the city. Last year, it was recognized as a UNESCO music venue and acknowledged its value of the city worldwide.

In economic and industrial terms, Daegu was at the heart of the economy as it was

the birthplace of the Samsung Group, a global company in the Republic of Korea. However, due to the delay in responding to changes in the global industrial environment, restructuring of local representative industries including textiles has not been achieved properly. The subsequent failure of local conglomerates and the failure of new entrants have reduced the flexibility of the labour market. At present, the city industry is composed mainly of parts industry (secondary industry) which cooperates with large manufacturing companies (Hyundai Automobile, Hyundai Dockyard, and POSCO) in the adjacent cities with a high proportion of urban service industries such as education, consumption and culture (tertiary industry). A total of 15,000 people from the higher education institutions, including Kyung-buk National University, migrate every year from 5,000 to 8,000 young people leaving for other cities.

Until the time when Kwon Young Jin, the 6th mayor directly elected by the citizens, entered the city (2014), the central government promoted the policy with a supplier-centred method of input (industrial complex infrastructure, and strategic industries promotion policy). The monopoly of the central government's budgeting functions and the low financial independence of the city made it difficult to escape interference and control of the central government's planned economy. Despite these policy efforts, the Gross Regional Product (GRDP) has been the lowest in the nation for 20 years, and as a result, the industrial structure has also failed to improve.

Since 2014, the city has tried to make new changes. We admit that we can no longer guarantee city development by industrial innovation alone, and revised the direction and goal of urban innovation from the fundament. Still, the city selected the upbringing industry and planned the investment, but started approaching it in a very different way from the previous one.

As the need to combine the level and scope of innovations has been disseminated to citizens, new initiatives have begun, involving citizens as subjects. In January 2015, in order to make Daegu a full creative and dynamic city, ***the Creative City Study Group*** was formed with citizens from all walks of life, including citizens, experts, youth students, students, and artists. With this in mind, ***the Creative City Forum*** (CEO: Prof. Kim Young Hwa) was formed and currently, about 2,000 creative citizens are participating in the panel. Citizen panels are involved in various types of living lab experiments that cope with industries, social and urban issues, and are also playing a key role in urban innovation platforms.

2 The City Innovation Platform and Daegu Living Labs

In order to enhance the substantiality and resilience of the urban ecosystem, it is necessary to combine the axis of innovation which centred on industrial innovation and the axis of innovation centred on social innovation. In the past, the two innovation systems had not been carried out in combination with each other. During the developing period of a city or a country, social innovation was focused on establishing networks to solve urban problems. Innovation systems on the level would face the limitations in the growth, whereas innovation systems on the scope would face the limitations in the recyclability and resources.

Therefore, **the vertical axis of innovation** cascading from the National Innovation System (NIS) to the Sectoral Innovation System (SIS), the Regional Innovation System (RIS), and the Innovation System of the enterprise, must be compromised with **the horizontal axis of innovation** that are expanding from individual, who have **the CEL DNA(Creativity-Empathy-Link)**, to instantly linking up to 1% of the city's population (Druker, 1993; Franz, 2015; Malerba, 2002).

We consider City Innovation Platform as a combination of the level and scope of innovation, and Daegu Living Labs as the substantialized form of this City Innovation Platform. In other words, during the process of achieving the Sustainable Development Goals of the city, the City Innovation Platform promoted the discovery and operation of the individual Living Labs.

Figure 1. The relationship between City Innovation Platform and Daegu Living Labs]

3 The Philosophy of City Innovation Platform

The total framework of the City Innovation Platform including Living Labs is depicted in the following graphics. The graphic is a modified version of “Open Innovation 2.0: A new Milieu” model presented by Curley & Salmeline (2016), specifically adjusted in the context of Daegu.

The philosophy of City Innovation Platform, which focuses on City Innovation platform, can be summarized as follows.

Figure 2. The Philosophy of Daegu City Innovation Platform

**Open Innovation 2.0: A new Milieu (Curley & Salmelin, 2016)*, revised for City Innovation Platform.

Operating Systems

The operation of a platform is enabled when it secures the communication, methodology, and openness that allows each and every participant’ voluntary participation without marginalizing them. Therefore, the City Innovation platform is operated by utilizing the following five tools and systems:

Design Thinking, which involves stakeholders to define problems and create solutions, **Widersprüche Oriented Innovation System**, which creates new solutions while compromising contradiction between current resources and ideal goals in the process of creating solutions, **Socio-cracy**, which does not ignore the opinions of others and makes it to the end of the collective agreement, **Citizen Science**, which is dedicated to the common goals of the city with the spontaneity and dynamism of individual citizens, and **Open Data**, which organizes the recycling of data resources generated from the whole life cycle of the Living Labs, are applied as management principles (Buck, Villines, 2017; Curley, Salmelin, 2016 ; Herr, 2017; IDEO, 2011; Liedtka, Ogilvie, 2011; Robertson, 2015; Zurich Univ., 2015).

Goals

High sustainability to increase the recyclability of city resources to the next generation and high resilience to changes in the external environment are the ultimate goals of City Innovation Platform. In the process of living lab, the middle goal is to connect innovation entities, to find a lively and positive urban language, and to attract new human resources with talents (Landry, 2006; Lee, 2014; Hirvikoski, 2017).

All these goals are closely related to the UN's SDGs Agenda. The City Innovation Platform provides goals of the subunits and tools for evaluation in substantially implementing the UN's SDGs Agenda, such as Making resilient and sustainable city, ensuring learning opportunities, achieving gender equality, and Building resilient infrastructure.

Resources

Innovation Platform uses the three internal resources to operate the urban innovation platform. Smart Citizen, which is the goal and means of the living lab and also plays a role as the subject, the city's alley as the basic unit of space of innovation, and a lot of data created by space and people (Bror, 2017; Landry, 2000; Zurich Univ., 2015). People are subject and object of the City Innovation Platform, and they are at the centre of the utilized resources. The concept of resources is extended from citizens as the centre, to time and space from people. Resources of time are recorded as data and innovations are generated by managing the prototypes by versions or opening up the accumulated data. When it comes to resources of space, alleys are utilized as the basic unit. Since an alley is a minimum unit where the lives of city civilians intersect, it serves as the minimum unit where innovations happen.

4 Structures of Daegu Living Labs

We will divide Daegu Living Labs into two separate structures, superstructure and infrastructure, and describe both. The superstructure is directly connected to the City Innovation Platform, and the infrastructure is related to three forms of operation at a specific place and to Living Labs. We separated the process of discovering and training human resources, which is one of the most important factors of Living Labs. Thus, the superstructure is focused on training the facilitator and panels needed for various living labs operated in a specific place, and on improving their problem-solving capability. These training programs of the superstructure are operated under the titles of Creative Study Group, Focus Group, Social Dinning, Social Fiction School, and etc, including the program operation is implemented by the Creativity City Forum.

Superstructure

The superstructure of Daegu Living Labs focuses on the actual change mechanism that goes through the process of '**Stimulation-Training-Facilitation-Diffusion**'. First, in order for innovation to take place, the stimulus to recognize the need for change must be made naturally, and **The Creativity City Forum** operates an education and learning program that stimulates these changes. The next step in this program of change is to train citizens with the deepening process of **the Focus Research** which creates highly qualified policies in the areas of interests. **The Social Dining** is also used to build communities of interests and perform problem defining and solution planning by sector. The next step is training facilitators to organize the citizen panel through **the Social Fiction Civic School**, from making ideas of urban future to making prototypes. Once stimuli-training-facilitation is done, the panel will spread to various programs such as **the Open Topic Forum** and **the Creative City CEO Forum** to operate the change mechanism (Chesbrough, 2003; Landry, 2000). The superstructure of innovation is aimed at securing the Smart Citizen panels to spread innovation within the city and organizing the necessary infrastructure activities through the training of facilitators. Indicators were developed to measure the degree of innovation of the panels and facilitators participating in the superstructure. The VITAL index of H.S. Lee (2014) and CEL index of H.D Kim (2017) are typical tools.

Figure 3. The Progress of Superstructure of Daegu Living Labs

Infrastructure of City Innovation Platform

The Smart Citizens who were trained at the superstructure are experimenting Living Labs in various forms. Alley Living Lab, Social Living Lab, and Smart Living Labs are the representative forms of Living Labs. Each Living Lab has completely different direction and goals. Thus, we named them “Daegu Living Labs” to manage various living labs; to let them share common fundamental processes and human resources including facilitators, despite the differences in their goals and direction.

Daegu Living Labs are composed of step-by-step stages which are search, experiment, and evaluation (see Table 1). Activities at each stage are provided in a manual format. Each stage of the living lab is mapped to a technology development stage, and the required Civic Tech or Urban Tech is developed in an agile manner. As the process progresses, the generated data is designed to have a standardized data framework for a new service or next prototype (Schuurmann, 2015; Ståhlbröst & Marita, 2012; Almirall, Lee & Wareham, 2012).

Table 2. Activities according to Living Lab Performances

Technology Development Phase	Discovering Ideas	Conceptualization	Prototype Development	Before Release	Release	After Release
Living Lab Phase	A. Exploration		B. Experimentation	C. Evaluation		
Living Lab Performance	User behaviour analysis and 'conceptual design'		'Prototype development' and implementation	'Product and service development' and demonstration		
	① Problem-focused user behaviour analysis - General user behaviour analysis - Core User Behaviour Analysis ② Conceptual design of product/service for problem-solving - Collaborative design with users		① Prototype development - Prototype development through collaboration ② Prototype experiment and user feedback - Prototype installation and feedback - Participation observation, Participant satisfaction survey	① Development of products and services - Prototype development based on prototype results ② Product and service demonstration and feedback - feedback to extended users		
Preparatory Activities	① Design of living wrap propulsion system - Research topic setting - Participating organization and promotion system - Infrastructure construction: Clinical experiment and demonstration, site selection, related technology infrastructure - Intellectual property rights management regulations and legal system					

② **End-user organization**

- End-user group composition scheme
- User participation motivation plan
- User feedback collection (site visit, focus group interview, survey)
- Organization of training programs for users and technicians

Alley Living Lab: Urban Regeneration Model through

This was an early model of Daegu Living Labs, and many living lab models were experimented in the process of reclaiming old urban alleys. A representative success story is **Kim Gwang Seok Street** (a famous Korean folk song singer in the 1980s) where young artists defined the problems in the alley with the inhabited citizens and succeeded in regenerating the city by creating works of art using alley walls. In addition, the handicraftsmen of the old and original city centres participated in the renovation of the alleys and created a new festival prototype called **the Tool Festival in Bukseongro Street**. There is also **the Modern Alley Living Lab** where residents of the unrecognized modern alleys restored historical contents, further created a new job as an **'Alley Commentator'**. The city is expanding user participation innovation centred on more alleys.

Social Living Lab: Urban Problem Solving and Social Venture Diffusion

In 2017, Daegu is creating a new youth culture that uses real-life space as a laboratory centered on trained youth facilitators, who find solutions to social problems through co-work with various stakeholders in the city (Table 2).

We support young people strengthening the living lab's capabilities through education, mentoring, consulting, etc. so that they can discover their own social problems and find solutions. They are becoming 'social start-up' or 'social venture' by discovering social business model based on social innovation idea.

Table 3. Social Living Lab Project Lists

Project Name	Content of the Project
Earth Market #	Planning a meal with conversation and culture for young people eating alone
476 Project	Lectures and lectures are held in the provinces through crowdfunding method for lectures, cultural performances and information gap in local and metropolitan areas

Flosbebe	Solving psychological and economic problems through collaboration activities of single mothers
Knunyang (CAT)	Prepare a plan for creating an environment where street cats and people live together
Nurira Project	Youth activities that guide students to commute safely
UNIAS	Resolving the problem of unauthorized speculation of college trailer village waste
KWANUMDONG LivingLab	Improving communal spaces (parks) and creating a safe environment for elementary school students
BANDI Cops.	Activation of use of environment improvement of parks in neighborhood and creation of theme parks
DTC in Daegu	Cultural contents development that each university can exchange and young people can communicate
Media Dalgona	Producing independent publications dealing with stories of local youths rather than metropolitan areas

Smart City based on *Smart Living Lab*

Many cities in Korea, which have excellent information and communication infrastructure, are very competitive in adopting Smart City. Unlike other cities that are built focused on hardware, Daegu uses various ICT technologies to address various urban problems and approaches to solve specific problems with the public, citizens, private companies, universities, and support agencies together. To this end, we are designing ***the Smart Living Lab Platform*** in which a large number of citizens are able to participate. Daegu Smart City is focused on how many citizen panels participated in the problem to create a common solution, rather than how advanced technologies are adopted.

In 2016, ***the Digital Twin City*** is being built in cyberspace as well as building advanced ICT infrastructures on the physical space of Suseong Alpha District (southwest of Daegu City). On that, ***the Smart Living Lab*** will be operated by residents who use ICT tools in areas such as energy, autonomous mobility, and urban disaster management. Data is refined, standardized and opened to enable new business models and products to be actively developed within the Smart Living Lab.

Figure 4. Smart Living Lab in Daegu

Connection of Superstructure and Infrastructure

In the above, we explained the structure of Daegu Living Labs and the mechanism by which Daegu's innovative platform works. The infrastructure where various living lab models are experimented in concrete space and superstructure where they are nurtured and spread are connected, and mutual feedback is exchanged, while expanding throughout the city gradually. ***The Living Lab Governance*** and ***the Creative City Global Forum*** mediate these interconnections.

The Daegu Living Labs Governance is a network organization composed of operators and facilitators of individual living labs. Organizations will explore the future agenda of urban innovation and provide manual for standardization of living labs. The standard manual consists of implantable hierarchy modules, including panel acquisition, data management, problem definition, solution exploration, experimentation, evaluation process, specific user tools, and training programs. Organizations also conduct activities necessary to open up and standardize city-owned data, as well as to identify citizen-participatory business models.

The Creative City Global Forum plays a role in spreading out the superstructure and infrastructure of the Daegu Living Labs. The Forum is a festival venue to showcase the performance of various Living Labs being experimented in the city and to provide deepened workshop training for participating panels of the urban

innovation platform. Through the Creative City Global Forum in 2017, we signed the MOU with the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL).

Pictures from Office of Daegu Creative City Global Forum

The Roles of Daegu Living Labs for Sustainable Development Goals

Various forms of Daegu Living Labs are substantially operated in direct and indirect connections with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that UN adopted for its goal of “Transforming our world.”

Specifically, Alley Living Lab, which solves problems of old city alleys with the inhabited citizens, is related to “Making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable” (Goal 11). Social Living Lab, which is operated with the purpose of urban problem solving and social venture diffusion, is faithfully performing the agendas of “Ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all” (Goal 4) and “Achieving gender equality and empower all women and girls” (Goal 5), in their individual projects. Smart Living Lab, accompanied by a large-scale input of human resources and infrastructure, is implementing the agendas of “Ensuring access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all” (Goal 7) and “Building resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation” (Goal 9)

Daegu Living Labs Governance is providing the learning opportunities of SDGs Agenda during the training of Smart Citizens and facilitators and monitoring the operational processes by making specific standards. Specialists from various fields and citizen panels participate in designing the standards.

5 Conclusion

We introduced the structure and operation mechanism of **Daegu Living Labs**, which are being experimented with **the City Innovation Platform** in Daegu. For a long time, Daegu has been experimenting with community-based co-creation focusing on the **alleys** and is currently expanding throughout the city with several living labs. Various living labs have been tested, but we are still young and evolving.

Daegu Living Labs have produced many meaningful results by organically operating the upper and lower structures. With the expansion of the living labs, a large number of voluntary citizen panels have been secured, and direct democracy has been activated, such as **the Citizens Roundtable**, **the People's Participation Budget System**, and the urban innovation density has increased as **the multi-innovation layers of Dot (Individual) - Line (Alley) - Area (Living Lab)** are connected. Every time smart city services or new public policies was provided, rather than the existing top-down approach, the use of living lab approach (bottom-up) was given priority, helping start-ups and young people experiment with various paths of social entry.

By doing so, Daegu Living Labs are supporting the city to substantially realize the UN's SDGs Agenda, such as Making resilient and sustainable city, ensuring lifelong learning opportunities, achieving gender equality, Building resilient infrastructure. Daegu Living Labs Governance established the system to manage and evaluate SDGs Agenda to make it the first interest in fostering an innovation ecosystem approach in Daegu.

There still are problems that remain. The problems provide us with the opportunity and challenge for the advanced studies. They will be sophisticated standardization of Living Labs model as City Innovation Platform and of data, A time-series analysis of the SDGs achievement in each Living Lab, and conflict management and leadership issue during the process of implementing the SDGs.

To do this, more and more living labs are needed in the city, and advanced networks like ENoLL need to be activated. The solidarity among living labs enables to making cross-validation, joint learning, and interchange of prototype data. This will lead to more smart citizens, agency organizations, and facilitators connecting and creating a more resilient and sustainable city.

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